

PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN'S ATTENTION

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Abstract: This article describes the process of analyzing the attention of preschool children.

Key words: types of attention, voluntary attention, involuntary attention, voluntary attention, attention training, method of observation.

Attention begins to develop very early in children. Although 1-2 week old babies do not show any signs of attention, from the age of 1 month, signs of voluntary attention begin to appear. Attention is divided into 3 types:

Voluntary attention - as a higher type of attention, is formed in the work process. Voluntary attention occurs if a person has set a certain task for himself in the course of his activity and has consciously developed an action program. Direct interest plays a big role in involuntary attention. Something that is interesting, emotional, and enjoyable requires attention to be visible for a long time.

Post-voluntary attention - if attention from a goal-oriented activity is not only the result of the activity, but its content and process itself is interesting and important, as in the case of voluntary attention, then this post-voluntary attention is correct. gives an incentive to reflect on. The development of preschool children's attention depends not only on the conditions in the preschool educational institution, but to a large extent on the family conditions as well. That is why children's attention does not develop evenly and at the same level. For example, some children cannot regulate their behavior and behavior because they are not under proper control in the family or because they are sent to be too strong. Such children cannot sit still in a place where they touch everything without permission. Since the attention of such children is very unstable, they cannot concentrate on anything. We use the following methods and exercises to develop the attention of preschool children.

"Attention exercise" before working with the blackboard, the educator tells the children about the furniture of the room one by one. For example, a desk, a flower, a

painting, a ceiling, a shelf, etc., and at the end of the lesson, the children draw their attention to the blackboard by saying "Blackboard" in a loud voice.

In my opinion, this method is very effective. The results of research show that students pay more attention to the volume and the fun of pronunciation. When this method is used, almost all children in the room pay attention to the blackboard and consciously prepare themselves to receive new information from the teacher. "Observability" method. In this method, children are given the task of remembering and fully describing the way from their home to preschool educational institution. This task is performed orally by students of the kata group. Educators make up for the shortcomings of the participating child. In this game, the child's visual memory and attention span are determined. Through the above method, it is possible to develop the attention and memory of some children, but as a result of observations, it can be seen that this method is somewhat controversial. Because if we take into account that the children who live in the neighborhood come to the pre-school educational institution, most of the children describe the same scenes, but this method cannot be said to be completely ineffective. This method is used in the educational process lessons of the special education systemis being organized in this way. It makes it easier for hearing-impaired children to focus.

Thus, every method and didactic exercise has its place and effect. Only a skilled educator, a master of his work, should know when and to which children he applies these methods. In conclusion, I can say that the methods and exercises mentioned above should be an integral part of every teacher's lesson. We believe that today's educators use such methods to expand the knowledge potential of children and bring them up to be able to compete with the youth of developed countries in every field.

References

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